

A Legal Guide to Immigration Detention in Italy

An English overview of the Italian, European and international legal framework that governs immigration detention in Italy

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The contents of this booklet are not legal advice

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legal framework that governs immigration detention in Italy*

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Part I: Italian Law on Immigration Detention

Decreto Legislativo 286/1998

Testo unico delle disposizioni concernenti la disciplina dell'immigrazione e norme sulla condizione dello straniero (Testo Unico Immigrazione) - Unified Text on measures concerning immigration and norms on the status of foreign citizens (Unified Text on Immigration)

Introduction

The legal provisions concerning migration in Italy are gathered in the “Unified Text on measures concerning immigration and norms on the condition of foreign citizens” (or the “Unified Text on Immigration”), which was first issued in 1998 (**Legislative Decree 286/1998**)¹ and subsequently modified and integrated.

The most relevant changes were introduced by **Law 189/2002** “Amendments to the legislation on immigration and asylum”, better known as “Bossi-Fini Law”. The measures introduced by Law 189/2002 were further tightened by the so-called “security decree” (**Law Decree 92/2008**) and a year later by **Law 94/2009**, better known as the “security package”. The “security package” introduced, for the first time in Italy, the so-called “crime of illegal immigration”, giving irregular stay a new degree of illegality, in addition to the usual administrative penalties. The relevant provisions were added or modified by **Law Decree 89/2011** (transposition of **Directive 2008/115/EC** and the full implementation of **Directive 2004/38/EC**) which marked a softening of some of the previously existing repressive measures following the decisions of the European Court of Justice² and the Italian Constitutional Court³. However, Law Decree 89/2011 has nevertheless failed to address some gaps between the EU Directive 2008/115 and Italian migration law⁴.

Relevant provisions of the Unified Text on Immigration (hereinafter referred to as UTI): Article 10, Article 13, Article 14 and Article 19.

Terminology (According to EU Directive 2008/115/EC, Article 3)

- *Return*: the process of a third-country national going back, whether in voluntary compliance with an obligation to return, or enforced to:
 - his or her country of origin, or

¹ *Decreto Legislativo 25 luglio 1998, n. 286 “Testo unico delle disposizioni concernenti la disciplina dell'immigrazione e norme sulla condizione dello straniero” (GU n. 191 del 18-8-1998 - Supplemento Ordinario n. 139) (“Testo Unico Immigrazione”).* Legislative Decree 25 July 1998, n. 286 “Unified text on provisions concerning immigration and norms on the condition of foreign citizens” (GU n. 191 of 18-8-1998 – Ordinary Supplement n. 139) (“Unified Text on Immigration”).

² *El Dridi* Case C-61/11 PPU, Court of Justice of the European Union, judgment of 28 April 2011.

³ *Corte Costituzionale, sentenza n. 359 del 13 dicembre 2010.* Constitutional Court, judgement n. 359 of 13 December 2010; *Corte Costituzionale, sentenza n. 115 del 4 aprile 2011.* Constitutional Court, judgement n. 115 of 4 April 2011; *Corte Costituzionale, sentenza n. 164 del 12 maggio 2011.* Constitutional Court, judgement n. 164 of 12 May 2011; *Corte Costituzionale, sentenza n. 245 del 20 luglio 2011.* Constitutional Court, judgement n. 245 of 20 July 2011.

⁴ See Part II, “Gaps between Directive 2008/115/EC and the corresponding Italian legislation”.

- a country of transit in accordance with Community or bilateral readmission agreements or other arrangements, or
- another third country, to which the third-country national concerned voluntarily decides to return and in which he or she will be accepted.
- *Return decision*: an administrative or judicial decision or act, stating or declaring the stay of a third-country national to be illegal and imposing or stating an obligation to return.
- *Removal*: the enforcement of the obligation to return, namely the physical transportation out of the Member State.
- *Entry ban*: an administrative or judicial decision or act prohibiting entry into and stay on the territory of the Member States for a specified period, accompanying a return decision.
- *Risk of absconding*: the existence of reasons in an individual case, which are based on objective criteria defined by law to believe that a third-country national who is the subject of return procedures may abscond.
- *Voluntary departure*: compliance with the obligation to return within the time-limit fixed for that purpose in the return decision.
- *Vulnerable persons*: minors, unaccompanied minors, disabled people, elderly people, pregnant women, single parents with minor children and persons who have been subjected to torture, rape or other serious forms of psychological, physical or sexual violence.

An Outline

- Types of return decision:
 - border rejections, implemented by the police or the Questore/Questura⁵ (**art. 10 UTI**);
 - return decision issued by the Ministry of the Interior (**art. 13.1 UTI**);
 - return decision issued by the Prefetto/Prefettura (**art. 13.2 UTI**); or
 - return decision issued by the judge.
- Types of removal enforcement:
 - voluntary return (**art. 13.5 UTI**);
 - forced return:
 - immediate accompaniment to the border (**art. 13.4 UTI**) + judicial validation (**art. 13.5 bis UTI**)
 - alternative measures to detention (**art. 14.1 bis UTI**) + judicial validation (**art. 14.1 bis UTI**)
 - detention (**art. 14 UTI**) + judicial validation (**artt. 14.3-4-5 UTI**)
 - invitation/order to leave the country within seven days (**art. 14.5 bis UTI**)

Return Decision (Art. 13 UTI)

Cases in which a removal may be ordered:

- *Return decision issued by the Ministry of the Interior* for reasons of public order and national security (**art. 13.1 UTI**);

⁵ The *Questura* is an office of the *Polizia di Stato* that is under the authority of the Ministry of the Interior and is competent in the territory of the province (*Provincia*) where it is located. *Questura*'s main function consists in maintaining order and ensuring public security within the territory of the province. The *Questore* is the head of the Italian *Questura*.

- *Return decision issued by the Prefetto* when:
 - the foreigner entered the country avoiding border controls and was not rejected;
 - the foreigner overstayed in the country after their residence permit was refused or revoked or if their residence permit expired more than sixty days ago and they did not applied to renew it;
 - the foreigner entered on the basis of a short-stay visa and failed to declare his presence within eight days or failed to leave the country within ninety days;
 - the foreigner poses a risk to public policy or national security in virtue of his criminal background (**art. 13.2 UTI**); or
- *Return decision issued by the judge as a security measure* against a foreigner convicted of distinctive crimes under the Code of Penal Procedure, if the foreigner is found to be “socially dangerous”;
- *Return decision issued by the judge as an alternative sanction to detention*, in case the foreigner has been :
 - subject to imprisonment for more than two years;
 - subject to a restraining order [*ordinanza restrittiva*] for distinctive crimes against the State; or
 - sentenced for the crime of irregular entry and stay.

Forced Return (Art. 13.4 UTI)

The *removal is enforced by the Questore through accompaniment to the national borders by the police*, the so-called “forced return”:

- a) in the cases provided for by **art. 13.1** and **art. 13.2.c UTI**;
- b) when there is a risk of absconding (**art. 13.4 bis UTI**);
- c) when the request for the residence permit has been dismissed as manifestly unfounded or fraudulent;
- d) when the foreigner did not comply with the time-limit fixed for his voluntary departure (**art. 13.5 UTI**) without a justified reason;
- e) when the foreigner violated one of the measures provided for by **art. 13.5.2** or by **art. 14.1 bis UTI**;
- f) when the removal has been ordered by the judge as a criminal sanction or as the consequence of a criminal sanction;
- g) in the case provided for by **art. 13.5.1 UTI**.

Risk of Absconding (Art. 13.4 bis UTI)

On the basis of at least one of the following circumstances, the Prefetto⁶ assesses the risk that the foreigner may try to avoid the voluntary departure procedure:

- a) lacking of a valid passport;
- b) lacking of documents concerning a house where the foreigner can be easily tracked down;
- c) previous declaration of a fake identity;
- d) previous violation of the voluntary departure procedure or of the entry ban;
- e) previous violation of one of the measures provided for by **art. 13.5.2 UTI**.

⁶ The *Prefetto* is the head of the Italian *Prefettura*. The *Prefettura* is the local branch of the Ministry of the Interior and it represents the central government at a local level. In each of the 110 Italian provinces (*Province*) there is a *Prefettura*. *Prefettura* offices manage issues such as order and public security, civil rights and immigration, local autonomies and voting matters.

Voluntary Departure (Art. 13.5 UTI)

This procedure was originally limited to certain categories of highly vulnerable foreigners, such as victims of trafficking, asylum seekers, etc., whilst the general rule for all other undocumented migrants was forced return (Law 94/2009). Following Directive 2008/115/EC, Italy was forced to implement the so-called “gradually increasing intensity” procedure.

Actually Law Decree 89/2011 does not clearly state that the removal of the foreign citizen should normally be enforced without any coercive measure and that the “default” procedure should be that of voluntary departure. On the contrary, the same law provides that a time-limit for the voluntary departure may be granted by the Prefetto to a foreign citizen who applies for it (therefore, it is not automatically operating) and only if none of the circumstances listed in **art. 13.4 UTI** occur. Otherwise, the foreigner is to be immediately accompanied to the national border.

The Prefetto evaluates each individual situation on a “case by case” basis and allows the foreigner a period of time which can vary from seven to thirty days to leave the country. Where necessary, this term may be extended, according to certain circumstances, such as:

- length of stay in the country;
- presence of children attending school or other family and social relationships; and
- admission to specific programs of “assisted voluntary return” (**art. 14 ter UTI**).

Art. 13.5.1 UTI: The Questura is in charge of informing the foreigner of the chance to apply for the voluntary departure procedure, by means of multilingual prearranged forms. If no request is submitted, the removal of the foreigner will be enforced as provided for by **art. 13.4 UTI**.

Art. 13.5.2 UTI: If the Prefetto allows an extension of the time-limit for the voluntary departure, the foreigner must provide appropriate financial guarantees. Moreover they will be subject to one or more measures imposed by the Questore, such as:

- a) passport suspension (the passport should be given back to the foreigner before his departure);
- b) obligation to live in a previously identified house where he can be easily tracked down; and/or
- c) daily attendance at a police station until the day of departure.

Such measures are to be communicated by the Questore to the judge (Giudice di Pace)⁷ within forty-eight hours. The judge then validates, modifies or dismisses them within the next

⁷ The UTI literally uses the word “judge” in Italian, however this legislation is actually referring to a *Giudice di Pace*. A *Giudice di Pace* is a non-specialist small-claims judge who is in charge of resolving minor cases or disputes under civil, administrative or criminal law. In Italian, a *Giudice di Pace* is commonly called an “honorary judge” (*giudice onorario*) who is appointed by the Minister of Justice. *Giudici di Pace* are paid proportionally based on the number of matters that they decide, rather than the amount of time that they spend hearing and deliberating over matters. Selection is based on qualifications and generally the selected *Giudici di Pace* are law graduates who have obtained the qualification to practice law or who have exercised judicial functions. Unlike in some jurisdictions, in Italy it is not necessary to have years of experience as a lawyer or barrister before undertaking the *Giudice di Pace* role. The only further requirement is that a *Giudice di Pace* must be between thirty and sixty-five years of age. In criminal matters the *Giudice di Pace* does not have the power to imprison a person.

forty-eight hours. Non-compliance with any of the judge's orders entails the imposition of a fine from 3,000 to 18,000 Euros and immediate forced removal.

Forced Return Procedure (Art. 13.5 bis)

In the cases provided for by **art. 13.4 UTI**, the Questore is required to notify a judge within forty-eight hours of the deportation order (return decision). The enforcement of such measure is then suspended until the judge validates or dismisses the Questore's order via a "*camera di consiglio*" procedure⁸. Both the foreigner and his lawyer must be quickly informed and take part to the hearing and representatives from the Questura may also be present. The foreigner, who is granted free legal aid assistance, is entitled to choose their own lawyer or they will be granted a State-appointed lawyer. Foreigners also have the right to be assisted by an interpreter during the hearing.

The judge's validation must occur within forty-eight hours from the Questore's notification. While waiting for the validation hearing, the foreigner can be held in an immigration detention centre (CIE). If the judge rejects the order or the validation does not occur within forty-eight hours, then the return decision issued by the Questore has no further effect. On the contrary, after the validation, the removal order becomes enforceable and the foreigner can only appeal to the *Corte di Cassazione*⁹ in Rome. However, the *Corte di Cassazione* does not have the power to suspend the removal procedure and whose proceedings usually take a considerable amount of time (approx. one to two years).

Art. 13.7 UTI: Any order, decision or measure concerning the entry, the stay or the removal of a foreigner must be communicated to them along with an explanation of the appeal procedures and a translation in a known language.

Art. 13.12 UTI: If the expelled foreigner cannot be returned to their country of origin, they will be transferred to the State where they came from arriving to Italy.

Entry Ban (Art. 13.13 UTI)

A foreigner who was issued a deportation order cannot re-enter Italy, unless they are granted a special authorisation by the Ministry of the Interior. In case of a violation, the foreigner will face a criminal charge punishable with detention (one to four years imprisonment) and will be immediately subject to forced removal. In case of a new illegal entry, the punishment ranges from one to five years imprisonment (**art. 13.13 bis UTI**).

The entry ban has a three to five years length, a term that can be exceeded in case the foreigner represents a serious threat to public or national security. Voluntary departure of the foreigner within the set deadline may result in the lifting of the entry ban (**art. 13.14 UTI**).

Rejection (Art. 10 UTI)

As well as a deportation order, even border rejection can entail detention in CIE (see **art. 14.1 UTI**).

⁸ *Camera di consiglio* is a special proceeding through which the dispute is resolved in a faster and private way, without audience with limited *istruttoria*. In the *istruttoria* phase the judge carries out investigations and acquires evidence and relevant information for the final judgement.

⁹ The *Corte di Cassazione* is the Italian Supreme Court located in Rome. It is a *giudice di legittimità*, which means that it cannot undertake merits review, as it only deals with interpretation of law and procedural correctness. Moreover, it solves conflicts about jurisdiction.

Art. 10.1 UTI: The border police may refuse entry to foreigners unable to meet legal requirements foreseen by the UTI.

Art. 10.2 UTI: Moreover, the *rejection with accompaniment to the border ordered by the Questore* may be applied to foreigners:

- a) who were stopped at the entry, while escaping border controls, or immediately after;
- b) who were temporarily allowed in the national territory on the ground of public assistance.

Art. 10.3 UTI: The carrier that took a foreigner to the national border without the required documents to enter the country, or a foreigner who must be anyhow rejected, is in charge of their immediate boarding and transferring back to the country that the foreigner came from.

Art. 10.4 UTI: The measures provided for by **art. 10.1** and **art. 10.2 UTI** do not apply in those cases envisaged by the existing provisions regulating political asylum, recognition of refugee status or the adoption of measures of temporary protection for humanitarian reasons.

Art. 10.5 UTI: The rejected foreigner is granted due assistance at national borders.

Art. 10.6 UTI: All rejections are recorded by the border police.

Enforcement of the Removal

As previously noted, irregular migrants cannot enter or reside in the country and they must be either rejected at the borders or removed. However, forced return is subject to both:

- legislative constraints:
the forced removal procedure does not apply to migrants who fall into the category of vulnerable persons (such as victims of trafficking and asylum seekers); to minors (unless they have to or decide to follow their expelled parent); to women who are pregnant or have given birth within the previous six months; etc.
- and practical constraints:
difficulties in the identification of irregular migrants and lack of cooperation from their countries of origin.

Currently there are three types of centres for irregular migrants in Italy:

- Reception Centres – *Centri di Accoglienza* – CDA (**Law 563/1995**);
- Reception Centres for Asylum Seekers – *Centri di Accoglienza per Richiedenti Asilo* - CARA (**Presidential Decree 303/2004** and **Legislative Decree 25/2008**);
- Centres for Identification and Expulsion – *Centri di Identificazione ed Espulsione* - CIE (**Law Decree 92/2008**) [former Temporary Detention Centres – CPT].

Centres for Identification and Expulsion (Art. 14 UTI)

A Centre for Identification and Expulsion (CIE) is an enclosed facility where foreigners, whose return decision cannot be immediately enforced, are confined under police surveillance while they wait to be identified and eventually deported.

Art. 14.1 UTI: When immediate removal is not possible due to *temporary conditions that hinder the preparation or the implementation of the deportation*, the Questore establishes that the foreigner must be detained in the closest CIE. Circumstances justifying such detention – that should be as short as possible - are limited to:

- the risk of absconding (as defined by **art. 13.4 bis UTI**);
- the need to provide the foreigner with assistance;
- the need to inquire into the foreigner's identity and nationality or to prepare their travel documents; and
- unavailability of a suitable means of transport.

Art. 14.1 bis UTI: If the foreigner holds their own passport and does not pose risk to public policy and public or national security, instead of detention in CIE, the Questore can decide to impose one or more of the following measures:

- a) passport suspension (the passport should be given back to the foreigner before their departure);
- b) obligation to live in a previously identified house where they can be easily tracked down; and/or
- c) daily attendance at a police station until the day of departure.

Such measures are to be communicated by the Questore within forty-eight hours to the judge, who validates, modifies or dismisses them within the next forty-eight hours. Non-compliance with any of these measures entails the imposition of a fine from 3,000 to 18,000 Euros and immediate forced removal.

Art. 14.2 UTI: The detained foreigner must be granted due assistance and full respect of his personal dignity. Freedom of correspondence and telephone communications are guaranteed as well.

Art. 14.3 UTI: Within forty-eight hours from the order's issue, all the documents relevant with the file must be submitted by the Questore to the judge.

Art. 14.4: The judge has to validate or dismiss the detention order within the next forty-eight hours. If no validation occurs within the set deadline, the order has no further effect and the foreigner must be released from CIE. Both the foreigner and his lawyer must be promptly informed about the hearing and take part in it, as well as the representatives from Questura. The foreigner, who is granted free legal aid assistance, is entitled to choose their own lawyer or they will be granted a State-appointed lawyer. Foreigners also have the right to be assisted by an interpreter during the hearing.

Art. 14.5 UTI: Judicial validation entails thirty days of detention in CIE. Whenever serious hurdles hamper the assessment of the foreigner's identity or nationality or the acquirement of travel documents, the Questore can request the judge a thirty day extension of the detention period. After the first sixty days, if the circumstances listed under **art. 14.1 UTI** still persist, the Questore may request the judge an additional sixty days of detention and a third extension of further sixty days can follow on the same ground. The length of detention must not exceed one hundred and eighty days. If after this period, despite fulfilling all reasonable efforts, the Questore did not enforce the deportation (the foreigner) due to their lack of cooperation or due to delays in obtaining documents from their country of origin, the Questore may request further extensions of detention of sixty days each, up to a maximum of additional twelve months. However, the Questore may enforce the removal at any moment, even before the term expires, immediately informing the judge. As a result, the length of detention in CIE may vary from thirty days to a maximum of eighteen months.

Art. 14.5 bis UTI: If detention could not be implemented or proved to be unsuccessful, the Questore orders the foreigner to leave the country on his own within seven days.

Art. 14.5 ter UTI: In the event that this measure is not observed without a justified reason, the foreigner is subject to a fine of 6,000 to 20,000 Euros and the foreigner could be issued a new deportation order and possibly detained again in CIE.

Art. 14.5 quater UTI: If the foreigner violates this last return decision with no justified reason, they will face a new fine of 15,000 to 30,000 Euros and they will be subject to another removal.

Art. 14.7 UTI: By means of the police, the Questore implements effective surveillance in order to avoid foreigners escaping from the CIE. In case of getaway, the Questore issues a new detention order, but the length of the previous detention is added to the second one not to exceed limits set by **art. 14.5 UTI**.

Prohibition to Return and Reject (Art. 19 UTI)

Art. 19.1 UTI: No return decision or rejection can be issued or enforced towards a country where the concerned foreigner could be subject to persecution on the grounds of race, sex, language, nationality, religion, political opinions, personal or social conditions, or where they could risk being rejected to another country where they would not be protected from such persecution.

Art. 19.2 UTI: With the exception of the cases provided for by **art. 13.1 TUI**, a return decision cannot be enforced towards:

- a) minors (under eighteen years old), except for their right to follow a parent subject to a return decision;
- b) foreigners holding a long-term residence permit ("*Permesso di soggiorno CE per soggiornanti di lungo periodo*"), except for provisions set forth in **art. 9 TUI**;
- c) foreigners co-habiting with their Italian relatives (within the 2nd degree) or with their Italian spouse;
- d) women who are pregnant or have given birth in the previous six months.

Decreto del Presidente della Repubblica 394/1999

Regolamento recante norme di attuazione del testo unico delle disposizioni concernenti la disciplina dell'immigrazione e norme sulla condizione dello straniero - "Regulation for the enforcement of the Unified Text on measures concerning immigration and norms on the status of foreign citizens"

Relevant provisions of Presidential Decree 394/1999¹⁰: Article 20, Article 21 and Article 22

Detention in CIEs (Art. 20 UTI)

Art. 20.1: The measure through which the Questore orders the detention of a foreigner in the closest CIE (according to availability of places) is communicated to the foreigner together with the rejection order or the return decision.

Art. 20.2: Through the same communication the foreigner is also informed of their right to a defence (to be exercised throughout the validation procedure).

Art. 20.3: The foreigner is furthermore informed that, in case of escaping from CIE, detention will be restored by the police

Art. 20.4: Detention in CIE cannot last more than what is strictly necessary for the enforcement of the rejection order or the return decision; in any case it cannot exceed the time-limit set forth in the UTI and it must definitely end if the Questore's order is not validated by the judge.

Art. 20.5: The validation procedure cannot cause a delay in the enforcement of the rejection order.

Patterns of Detention (Art. 21 UTI)

Art. 21.1: During their detention in CIE, the foreigner is guaranteed, with due respect to the communal living:

- freedom to talk within the centre and to visitors, in particular to lawyer and religious personnel;
- freedom of correspondence and of telephone communication; and
- respect of their fundamental human rights.

The above provisions, however, do not disregard the absolute ban on absconding from the CIE.

Art. 21.2: Inside the CIE, the foreigner is guaranteed:

- subsistence and assistance;
- essential health services;
- activities of socialisation;

¹⁰ *Decreto del Presidente della Repubblica 31 agosto 1999, n. 394 "Regolamento recante norme di attuazione del testo unico delle disposizioni concernenti la disciplina dell'immigrazione e norme sulla condizione dello straniero, a norma dell'articolo 1, comma 6, del decreto legislativo 25 luglio 1998, n. 286" (GU n. 258 del 3-11-1999 - Supplemento Ordinario n. 190).* Presidential Decree 31 August 1999, n. 394 "Regulation for the enforcement of the Unified Text on measures concerning immigration and norms on the status of foreign citizens, as provided for by art. 1.6 of legislative Decree 25 July 1998, n. 286" (GU n. 258 of 3-11-1999 - Ordinary Supplement n. 190).

- freedom of worship
within the limits set by the Constitution.

Art. 21.3: In order to guarantee freedom of correspondence and of telephone communication, a Ministerial Decree regulates access to telephone, telegraph and mail services in CIE and limits to financial contribution by the CIE staff (see “**Decreto Ministeriale 15 gennaio 2001**” below).

Art. 21.4: A foreigner can only be detained in CIEs (as identified by **art. 14.1 UTI**) or in hospitals in case of an urgent need for medical assistance.

Art. 21.5: If a foreigner needs to access a hospital, judiciary premises, their embassy or their consulate, they must be accompanied by the police and an order must be issued by the Questore.

Art. 21.6: In case of an imminent risk to the life of a close relative living in Italy or for other serious and exceptional reasons, a judge, after asking for the Questore’s opinion, may authorise a detainee to leave the CIE for the strictly necessary amount of time. The foreigner will be accompanied by the police.

Art. 21.7: Besides CIE personnel, police, the Questore and judges, the following people are also allowed to enter inside CIE:

- co-habiting relatives of the detainee;
- their lawyer;
- religious personnel;
- staff of the foreigner’s embassy or consulate; and
- members of public institutions, associations and NGOs that are authorised to carry out assistance activities inside CIE under **art. 22** or authorised on the basis of specific projects of cooperation agreed with the local Prefettura.

Art. 21.8: All the rules concerning communal living, activities and services offered inside the CIE are established by the Prefetto, after consulting the Questore. Such rules implement the provisions provided for in the Decree establishing the CIE and in the Ministerial Decree, which are consistent with the aims set by **art. 14.9 UTI**.

Art. 21.9: All other measures concerning safety, security and public order inside the CIE are decided by the Questore, who may ask, even by means of the police, the needed collaboration by the CIE manager and personnel, who are obliged to fulfil this duty.

The Functioning of CIEs (Art. 22 UTI)

Art. 22.1: The local Prefetto establishes and manages the CIE (as provided by **art. 21.8**) according to the instructions and rules issued by the Ministry of the Interior. The Prefetto may stipulate conventions with local authorities and private or public actors, which may also avail themselves of other NGOs, associations and social cooperatives.

Art. 22.3: The Prefetto identifies the person in charge of managing the CIE and monitors the administration and management of the CIE.

Art. 22.4: Inside the CIE, one or more rooms are available for the consular authorities to carry out their activities. Police should grant full cooperation with the consular personnel in

order to speed up identification procedures and the acquirement of documents that are necessary for repatriation.

Decreto Ministeriale 15 gennaio 2001

Modalità di utilizzo dei servizi telefonici, telegrafici e postali dei centri di identificazione ed espulsione nonché limiti di contribuzione alle spese da parte dell'Amministrazione dell'Interno – “Directions for use of telephone, telegraph and mail services in the Centres for Identification and Expulsion and limits to financial contribution by the Administration of the Ministry of the Interior”

Relevant provisions of Ministerial Decree 15 January 2001¹¹: Article 1, Article 2 and Article 4

Art. 1.1: Public telephones are available on payment (pre-paid cards or coins) inside CIE. There cannot be less than one telephone per twenty-five detainees.

Art. 1.2: Each detainee is granted a pre-paid card charged with 10,000 Lire [5 Euros] every ten days.

Art. 1.3: This card is given to the detainee at the beginning of the ten-day period. They do not have to give it back the moment their detention ends.

Art. 2.1: Detainees are guaranteed the use of mail and telegraph services. Privacy of their correspondence is also guaranteed.

Art. 2.2: Upon detainee's request, the CIE administration will cover their expenses for three letters and three telegraphs, up to a maximum of 30,000 Lire [15 Euros].

Art. 4.1: The Ministry of the Interior, together with the Treasury, redefines the amount of the contributions provided for by **art. 1** and **art. 2** in case of relevant increases or reductions in the mail, telegraph or telephone fares.

¹¹ *Decreto Ministeriale 15 gennaio 2001, “Modalità di utilizzo dei servizi telefonici, telegrafici e postali dei centri di identificazione ed espulsione nonché limiti di contribuzione alle spese da parte dell'Amministrazione dell'interno” (G.U. n. 63 del 16-03-2001).* Ministerial Decree of 15 January 2001, “Rules for the use of telephone, telegraph and postal services in centres for identification and expulsion, and the scope of the Ministry of the Interior's financial contribution” (G.U. n. 63 of 16-03-2001).

Validation Hearings, Extension Hearings and Relevant Rulings from the *Corte di Cassazione*

Validation and extension hearings are crucial steps in Italian immigration procedure, being the forums where judges rule on the validation or the extension of an undocumented migrant's detention. Consequently, the detainee and their lawyer should have all of the individual information and time to adequately access a full defence right. Detainees have the right to appoint a "trust lawyer" (*avvocato di fiducia*¹²) and if the detainee does not have their own "trust lawyer", the judge will designate a State-appointed lawyer (*avvocato d'ufficio*¹³). In both cases, detainees are granted access to free legal aid, meaning that they do not have to pay for their lawyer's work. The *avvocato d'ufficio* are generally appointed on the morning of the validation or extension hearings, and as a result the lack of time to adequately prepare cases is a recurrent issue raised by lawyers working within the system.

Since 2010 the *Corte di Cassazione* ruled to confirm that detainees should take part not only to validation hearings, but also to all extension hearings (cases number 4544/2010, 10290/2010, 13117/2011, 13767/2011, 9596/2012 and 10055/2012). However, there are serious questions as to whether this right is actually being complied with by judges throughout Italy¹⁴. This led the *Corte di Cassazione* to reaffirm its guidance in a recent decision issued on the 13th June 2012:

*"[...] [T]his Court has recently proceeded to consider the law secundum constitutionem (Cass. 4544 and 10290, 2010; Cass. 13117 and 13767, 2011) and reached the conclusion that the same guarantees of contraddittorio should be applied to extension hearings, consisting of the necessary participation of a legal representative and of hearing the detainee himself, as is explicitly foreseen for validation hearings, under art. 14.4 Law Decree 286/1998"*¹⁵.

¹² An *avvocato di fiducia* is a lawyer whom a person has individually chosen to represent them for a case.

¹³ In the Italian legal system, an *avvocato d'ufficio* is the lawyer who is appointed by the judge in cases where legal assistance is required by law but a person did not designate their own lawyer.

¹⁴ See Ulrich Stege et al. *Betwixt and Between: A Human Rights Investigation into Turin's Immigration Detention Centre*, International University College of Turin, September 2012, p. 65.

¹⁵ *"[...] [Q]uesta Corte ha proceduto di recente alla doverosa lettura secundum constitutionem delle norme stesse (Cass. 4544 e 10290 del 2010, 13117 e 13767 del 2011) pervenendo alla conclusione per la quale al sub procedimento di concessione della proroga devono essere applicate le stesse garanzie del contraddittorio, consistenti nella partecipazione necessaria del difensore e nell'audizione dell'interessato che sono previste esplicitamente, ai sensi dell'art. 14, quarto comma, del d.lgs. n. 286 del 1998, nel procedimento di convalida della prima frazione temporale dell'trattenimento"*, *Corte di Cassazione, Sezioni Unite Civili, ordinanza del 13 giugno 2012, n. 9596*. Supreme Court, Unified Civil Section, order of 13 June 2012, n. 9596; see also *Corte di Cassazione, Sezione VI Civile, ordinanza del 19 giugno 2012, n. 10055*. Supreme Court, Civil Section VI, order of 19 June 2012, n. 10055.

Part II: European Union Law on Immigration Detention

The Relevance of EU Directives to the Legal Framework Governing Italian CIE

As an EU Member State, Italy is required to transpose the different EU directives into Italian national law by the date which is specified in each EU directive. After the date for transposition has elapsed, an individual has the power to claim the direct legal effect of an EU directive where:

- a) the wording of the directive is sufficiently clear and specific, and does not leave any discretion to Member States (for example if the directive adopts clear words denoting obligation, such as “Member States shall...”); and
- b) the directive is individually applicable to the third country national in question.

Directive 2008/115/EC

Directive 2008/115/EC (“the Return Directive”)¹⁶ establishes common standards and procedures for Member States in cases in which third country nationals may be removed from their territories. It lays down rules aimed at implementing an effective return policy, to be carried out through a fair and transparent procedure. Member States must respect the principle of *non-refoulement* and take into consideration the best interests of the child, the right to family life and the health conditions of the people concerned. The objective of the Return Directive is to establish common rules for the return, removal and use of coercive measures and the detention of third country nationals in the EU’s territory.

The key features of the Return Directive include:

- a requirement for a fair and transparent procedure for return decisions affecting irregular migrants;
- an obligation on EU Member States to either return irregular migrants or to grant them legal status;
- decisions adopted on a case-by-case basis and based on objective criteria, beyond the mere fact of an illegal stay;
- the promotion of voluntary departure by establishing a general rule that “*an appropriate period for voluntary departure*”¹⁷ shall be granted;

¹⁶ Directive 2008/115/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 December 2008 on common standards and procedures in Member States for returning illegally staying third-country nationals, L 348/98 *Official Journal of the European Union*, 24.12.2008. On the Return Directive, see: Steve Peers, *EU Justice and Home Affairs Law*, 3rd ed., Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2011, 563-575; Diego Acosta, “The Good, the Bad, and the Ugly in EU Migration Law. Is the European Parliament Becoming Bad and Ugly?”, *European Journal of Migration and Law*, issue 11, 2009, pp. 19-39; Rosa Raffelli, “The returns directive in light of the El Dridi judgement”, *Perspectives on Federalism*, vol. 3, issue 1, 2011, pp. 32-45.

¹⁷ Directive 2008/115/EC, art. 7.

- the provision of a minimum set of basic rights for people residing irregularly, including access to health care and education;
- a limit to the use of coercive measures and the guarantee that such measures are not excessive or disproportionate;
- a limit to the use of detention and the establishment of a set of minimum safeguards for detainees.

Interpreting EU Directive 2008/115: Case Law from the European Court of Justice (ECJ)

Said Shamilovich Kadzoev (Huchbarov)¹⁸

The *Kadzoev* case sets out the rules on how to calculate the period of detention as limited by Arts. 15(4) to (6) of the Return Directive. The case also comments on the meaning of “reasonable prospects of removal” as a justification of detention under the Return Directive. The *Kadzoev* case clarified the rule that pre-removal detention cannot be extended after the expiration of its maximum length and pre-removal detention ceases to be justified when it appears that a reasonable prospect of removal no longer exists.

In *Kadzoev* the ECJ held that “Article 15(5) and (6) of Directive 2008/115 must be interpreted as meaning that the period during which execution of the decree of deportation was suspended because of a judicial review procedure brought against that decree by the person concerned is to be taken into account in calculating the period of detention for the purpose of removal, where the person concerned continued to be held in a detention facility during that procedure”¹⁹.

The ECJ then considered whether Article 15(4) of EU Directive 2008/115 is to be interpreted as meaning that there is no reasonable prospect of removal where the possibilities of extending the periods of detention provided for in Article 15(6) have been exhausted, in the situation where no agreement for readmission has been reached with the third country at the time when a judicial review of the detention of the person concerned is conducted. It was held that “Article 15(4) of Directive 2008/115 can thus only apply if the maximum periods of detention laid down in Article 15(5) and (6) of the directive have not expired [... and] Article 15(4) of Directive 2008/115 must be interpreted as not being applicable where the possibilities of extending the periods of detention provided for in Article 15(6) of Directive 2008/115 have been exhausted at the time when a judicial review of the detention of the person concerned is conducted”²⁰. When a national court reviews the lawfulness of detention, it must be satisfied “that a real prospect exists that the removal can be carried out successfully, having regard to the periods laid down in Article 15(5) and (6) of Directive 2008/115, for it to be possible to consider that there is a ‘reasonable prospect of removal’ within the meaning of Article 15(4) of that directive”.

¹⁸ *Case C-357/09 PPU*, Court of Justice of the European Union, judgment of 30 November 2009.

¹⁹ *Ibid.*, para. 57.

²⁰ *Ibid.*, paras. 61-62.

Thus a reasonable prospect of removal does not exist where it appears unlikely that the person concerned will be admitted to a third country, having regard to those periods.”²¹

Hassen El Dridi²²

The *El Dridi* case clarifies the scope of the application of Directive 2008/115/EC, with specific reference to the difference between pre-return detention and criminal detention. The ECJ ruled that Italy could not apply criminal detention as punishment to third country nationals who failed to comply with a deportation order, also considering that such measure would easily jeopardize the removal procedure as outlined in the Directive.

Alexandre Achughbabian²³

The *Achughbabian* case further clarified the *El Dridi* case by looking at the question of when the detention of an irregular third-country migrant is for the purposes of removal in contrast to when it is for the purpose of criminal imprisonment. The ECJ held that criminal provisions punishing irregular immigrants are not incompatible with Directive 2008/115/EC. However, there are limitations and conditions to this rule. The permissible criminal sanctions have a very limited scope and criminal provisions cannot be applied before or during the return procedure.

Md Sagor²⁴

The subsequent *Sagor* case relied on the *Achughbabian* case for the rule that:

“Directive 2008/115 concerns only the return of illegally staying third-country nationals and is thus not designed to harmonise in their entirety the rules of the Member States on the stay of foreign nationals. Therefore, that directive does not preclude the law of a Member State from classifying an illegal stay as an offence and laying down criminal sanctions to deter and penalise such an infringement.”²⁵

In *Sagor* case the *Tribunale di Rovigo* asked the ECJ to provide a legal opinion in the case of Mr Sagor, a third country national who had entered Italy in March 2009 and was staying in Italy irregularly without ever having possessed a residence permit. On 22 July 2012, Mr Sagor was summoned to the *Tribunale di Rovigo* for the offence of illegal entry or stay referred to in Article 10 of Legislative Decree 286/1998 (i.e. the UTI) and for the offence referred to in Article 6(3) of the same legislative decree.

The ECJ found that it had not been proved that Mr Sagor entered Italy illegally as it had not been demonstrated to the requisite legal standard that he avoided border controls. The ECJ agreed that on the fact that the offence of illegal stay had been proven. The *Sagor* case followed the *Achughbabian* case and *Sagor* served to clarify the rule that “a Member State may not apply criminal law rules which are liable to undermine the application of

²¹ Ibid., paras. 65-66.

²² *Case C-61/11 PPU*, Court of Justice of the European Union, judgment of 28 April 2011.

²³ *Case C-329/11*, Court of Justice of the European Union, judgment of 20 January 2012.

²⁴ *Case C-430/11*, Court of Justice of the European Union, judgment of 6 December 2012.

²⁵ In *Sagor*, para. 31 the Court states that this interpretive rule derives from *Achughbabian*, para. 28.

the common standards and procedures established by Directive 2008/115 and thus to deprive it of its effectiveness (see Case C-61/11 PPU *El Dridi* [2011] ECR I-0000, para. 55, and *Achughbalian*, para. 36)²⁶. Fines were found to be permissible criminal sanctions, however it is not permissible to penalise third-country nationals by means of “a home detention order without guaranteeing that the enforcement of that order must come to an end as soon as the physical transportation of the individual concerned out of that Member State is possible”²⁷.

Effective Remedy

When interpreting the meaning of “effective remedy” under Directive 2008/115 it is important to also recall Council of Europe law and the interpretation of “effective remedy” under Art. 13 ECHR²⁸. In addition, the interpretation of the words “effective remedy” under Directive 2005/85/EC is also relevant to understanding how effective remedy might be understood in the Return Directive. Consequently, the *Diouf* case²⁹ is worthy of consideration for its commentary on how effective remedy is understood by the ECJ in the context of Directive 2005/85/EC.

Gaps between Directive 2008/115/EC and the corresponding Italian Legislation

1. According to Directive 2008/115/EC, voluntary return should be the default rule and it should be preferred over forced return. Thus, article 7 of the Return Directive uses a mandatory language (i.e. the verb “shall” instead of “may”) in order to indicate that voluntary departure should be more of the rule than the exception. Even if the Return Directive establishes that Member States must guarantee a period in which voluntary departure is possible, the opposite is the norm in the Italian legislation (see Law Decree 89/2011 and articles 13 and 14 UTI). Moreover Law Decree 89/2011 does not clearly state that the removal of irregular migrants should normally be enforced without any coercive measure. A time-limit for voluntary departure may be granted by the Prefetto only to those who apply for it and therefore in Italy the voluntary departure procedure is neither automatic, nor a “default rule”.
2. Article 15(3) of Directive 2008/115/EC uses mandatory language in stating that judicial or administrative reviews must be provided either on the detainee’s request or on an *ex officio* basis (i.e. reviews that are automatic because established by law). Moreover, the Return Directive clarifies the rule that where a detainee faces prolonged detention periods, reviews must be subject to the supervision of a judicial authority. However, there is no provision under Italian law that permits detainees to request a review for their detention. Given that there is no provision which makes it possible for a detainee to request a review of their detention, detainees must wait up to thirty days for their first *ex*

²⁶ *Sagor*, para. 32.

²⁷ *Ibid.*, para. 47.

²⁸ See Part III, “The Right to an Effective Remedy”.

²⁹ *Brahim Samba Diouf v Ministre du Travail, de l’Emploi et de l’Immigration* Case C-69/10, Court of Justice of the European Union, judgment of 28 July 2011.

officio periodic review. After this first review (“extension hearing”) detainees must wait sixty days for all subsequent extension hearings that review the legitimacy of their detention. Furthermore, the *Giudice di Pace* who run the extension hearings are frequently criticised for merely supervising Questura’s engagement in attempting to finalise the removal. In practice, extension hearings rarely involve a comprehensive merits-based evaluation of the case for continuing to restrict the detainee’s liberty.

3. Article 15(4) of Directive 2008/115/EC states that when there is no longer any “*reasonable prospect of removal*” either on the basis of legal grounds or for other considerations, detention is no more justified and should immediately cease. However, this provision is yet to be incorporated into Italian legislation.
4. Article 16(4) of Directive 2008/115/EC states that “*relevant and competent national, international and nongovernmental organisations and bodies shall have the possibility to visit detention facilities*”. According to European law, whilst immigration detention centres can exist, human rights organisations should also be allowed to enter them in order to give legal and medical assistance and monitor the conditions in which migrants are temporarily detained. Although Italian law provides for NGOs and other associations to enter inside CIEs³⁰, there is clearly a lack of transparency in relation to the conditions by which permission to enter CIE is determined. There is also ambiguity as to the role that NGOs and social cooperatives can play inside CIE and it seems that their function is limited to providing goods, services and activities inside detention and they face serious barriers to meeting their second and equally important prescribed function of monitoring detention conditions³¹.

³⁰ See Presidential Decree 394/1999, art. 22.1.

³¹ See Presidential Decree 394/1999, art. 21.7.

EU Directives on Asylum

The right to political asylum and international humanitarian protection is a fundamental right and an international obligation. The right to seek asylum was first recognised in the *Convention Relating to the Status of Refugees* (“the Geneva Convention”)³² and it is now granted to people fleeing persecution or serious harm in their own country and who are, therefore, in need of international protection. An effective common policy on asylum is a constituent part of the EU objectives. At a European level, several legislative measures harmonising minimum standards concerning asylum have been adopted:

- Directive 2003/9/EC → minimum standards for the reception of asylum seekers;
- Directive 2004/83/EC → minimum standards for the qualification and status of third country nationals or stateless persons;
- Directive 2005/85/EC → minimum standards on procedures in Member States for granting and withdrawing refugee status.

Directive 2003/9/EC

Directive 2003/9/EC³³ sets out minimum standards for the reception of asylum applicants in EU Member States. The Directive applies to all third country nationals as well as to stateless people who have requested asylum at the border or on the territory of a Member State and to family members accompanying the applicant. Member States are free to apply more favourable conditions of reception and they may apply the same conditions to people who apply for forms of international protection different from those provided for by the Geneva Convention. The Directive establishes that applicants must be informed of their rights and of the benefits that they can claim, as well as the obligations that they have to comply with. Asylum seekers must receive a document certifying their status as asylum seekers. Member States must grant to asylum seekers freedom of movement within their territory and temporary detention is only allowed in order to check the identity of the applicant. Movement can be limited within certain geographical boundaries, but such limitations may only be compulsory for specific reasons. Member States must also guarantee certain material reception conditions (accommodation, food, clothing, etc.), family unit, medical and psychological care and access to the education system for minors. Special rules must be applied to people with special needs, such as minors, disabled people, elderly people and victims of discrimination or exploitation. Applicants must have the possibility to communicate with legal advisers and NGOs.

Directive 2004/83/EC

The main objective of Directive 2004/83/EC³⁴ is to ensure that Member States apply common

³² *Convention Relating to the Status of Refugees*, opened for signature 28 July 1951, 189 U.N.T.S.150 (entered into force 22 April 1954).

³³ Council Directive 2003/9/EC of 27 January 2003 laying down minimum standards for the reception of asylum seekers, L 31/18 *Official Journal of the European Union*, 6.2.2003.

³⁴ Council Directive 2004/83/EC of 29 April 2004 on minimum standards for the qualification and status of third country nationals or stateless persons as refugees or as persons who otherwise need international protection and the content of the protection granted, L 304/12 *Official Journal of the European Union*, 30.9.2004.

criteria for the identification of persons in need of international protection, and to ensure that a minimum level of benefits is available for these people in all Member States. Member States must guarantee a number of rights to people who qualify for refugee status or for subsidiary protection, i.e. those who cannot return to their country of origin due to a real risk of suffering serious harm. In order to make an assessment of who should be granted asylum or subsidiary protection, Member States must take into account facts relating to the country of origin, documentation or statements provided by the applicant, any evidence of either persecution or a real risk of enduring serious harm and the applicant's individual circumstances. Article 4(5) of the Directive provides the test for exceptions to the rule that applicants must be able to substantiate their application for international protection. This exception is relevant when a credible applicant has genuinely attempted to provide enough evidence to establish their claim however the applicant has not been able to obtain all of the necessary evidence due to forces outside of their control. Member States may introduce or retain more favourable standards for determining who qualifies for refugee status or subsidiary protection when determining the content of international protection, in so far as those standards are compatible with Directive 2004/83/EC.

Directive 2005/85/EC

Directive 2005/85/EC³⁵ aims to establish common standards and procedures for granting and withdrawing refugee status throughout the EU in the perspective of reducing differences between national legal systems. This should help to limit secondary movements of asylum seekers between Member States, where such movements would be caused by discrepancies in the legal framework. The Directive includes provisions on:

- procedural guarantees (information about procedures, access to legal assistance);
- minimum requirements for the decision-making process (decisions are to be taken individually, objectively and impartially, by personnel specialised in asylum matters and specifically trained for that purpose; decisions must be communicated in writing and a negative decision must be motivated); and
- the right to appeal a negative decision; and common standards for the application of certain concepts and practices.

The processing of asylum applications is left to the discretion of Member States, so that they may prioritise or accelerate the carrying out of any application, in accordance with their national needs whilst taking into account the standards set by this Directive. However, Member States may provide for special procedures, for example at the national border, that derogate from the principles and guarantees set by the Directive. Moreover, under specific conditions Member States can declare an application to be inadmissible and refuse to examine its merits. This might occur when another Member State has jurisdiction over determining the application or where another Member State has already granted the applicant refugee status.

³⁵ Council Directive 2005/85/EC of 1 December 2005 on minimum standards on procedures in Member States for granting and withdrawing refugee status, L 326/13 *Official Journal of the European Union*, 13.12.2005.

Part III: International and Council of Europe Human Rights Law

Introduction

Customary international law and treaty-based international law are founded on the principle of state sovereignty³⁶. It is a matter of well-established international law that, subject to its treaty obligations, a State has the right to control the entry of non-nationals into its territory³⁷. Italy has ratified numerous international instruments that limit when and how the State can detain people in CIE and the conditions under which such detention can or cannot occur.

Ten Guiding Principles on the Legality of Detention of Asylum Seekers and Irregular Migrants in Europe

The following ten principles on the legality of detention of asylum seekers and irregular migrants in Europe have been drawn from the international laws, Council of Europe law and EU laws which are applicable to all EU Member States³⁸:

1. *Detention of asylum seekers and irregular migrants shall be exceptional and only used after first reviewing all other alternatives and finding that there is no effective alternative;*
2. *Detention shall distinguish between asylum seekers and irregular migrants;*
3. *Detention shall be carried out by a procedure prescribed by law and authorised by a judicial authority and subject to a judicial periodic review;*
4. *Detention shall be ordered only for the specific purpose of preventing an unauthorised entry or with a view to deportation or extradition;*
5. *Detention shall not be arbitrary;*
6. *Detention shall only be used when necessary;*
7. *Detention shall be proportionate to the objective to be achieved;*
8. *The place, conditions and regime of detention shall be appropriate;*

³⁶ *Charter of the United Nations*, 24 October 1945, 1 UNTS XVI, chapter 1. art. 2.

³⁷ *Gül v Switzerland*, European Court of Human Rights, judgment of 19 February 1996, para. 38.

³⁸ These ten principles are cited from the Council of Europe's Parliamentary Assembly report published in January 2010 titled "The Detention of Asylum Seekers and Irregular Migrants in Europe". The rapporteur noted that international standards have not always been applied correctly, and sought to clarify international standards and to find common grounds where there have been differing approaches.

9. *Vulnerable people should not as a rule be placed in detention and specifically unaccompanied minor should never be detained; and*
10. *Detention must be for the shortest time possible.*

Right to Liberty and Security of Person

The right to liberty and security of person is recognised under the following international instruments that have been ratified by Italy:

Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR)

Article 3 of the UDHR states:

“Every-one has the right to... liberty and security of person”

Article 9 of the UDHR states:

“No one shall be subjected to arbitrary arrest, detention...”

International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR)

Article 9 of the ICCPR states:

“1. Everyone has the right to liberty and security of person. No one shall be subjected to arbitrary arrest or detention. No one shall be deprived of his liberty except on such grounds and in accordance with such procedure as are established by law.

2. Anyone who is arrested shall be informed, at the time of arrest, of the reasons for his arrest and shall be promptly informed of any charges against him.

3. Anyone arrested or detained on a criminal charge shall be brought promptly before a judge or other officer authorized by law to exercise judicial power and shall be entitled to trial within a reasonable time or to release. It shall not be the general rule that persons awaiting trial shall be detained in custody, but release may be subject to guarantees to appear for trial, at any other stage of the judicial proceedings, and, should occasion arise, for execution of the judgement.

4. Anyone who is deprived of his liberty by arrest or detention shall be entitled to take proceedings before a court, in order that that court may decide without delay on the lawfulness of his detention and order his release if the detention is not lawful.

5. Anyone who has been the victim of unlawful arrest or detention shall have an enforceable right to compensation.”

ICCPR test: What is “arbitrary arrest or detention”?

- Original interpretation:

“Unjust” or incompatible with the principles of justice or with the dignity of human person³⁹.

- Broader modern interpretation:

In *A v. Australia* the UN Human Rights Committee⁴⁰ noted that the meaning of “arbitrary” was more than simply “against the law”. The word “arbitrary” also included elements of inappropriateness, injustice and a lack of predictability and due process of law.

- Was the necessity of detention evaluated?

Detention is arbitrary if it is ordered without an objective assessment of its necessity.

- Detention as a consequence of exercising fundamental rights:

The UN Working Group on Arbitrary detention considered detention to be arbitrary “[w]hen detention is the result of judicial proceedings consequent upon, or a sentence arising from, the exercise by an individual of the rights and freedoms proclaimed in UDHR [...]”⁴¹, including the Article 14 right to seek asylum. This does not mean that immigration detention is illegal, however it does mean that detention cannot be a punishment for the mere fact that someone has attempted to exercise their UDHR right (i.e. detention cannot be a punishment for applying to seek asylum)

ICCPR Article 9(2) and ECHR Article 5(2) Test:

Anyone who has been arrested shall be informed in a language in which they understand⁴² at the time of their arrest, of the reasons for their arrest and shall be promptly informed of any charges against them.

Consider:

At the time of the arrest - was the person told of the reasons why they were being arrested?

Shortly after the arrest - was the person told of the charges against them?

The Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms (ECHR)

Article 5(1) of the ECHR states:

“1. Everyone has the right to liberty and security of person.

No one shall be deprived of his liberty save in the following cases and in accordance with a procedure prescribed by law:

(a) the lawful detention of a person after conviction by a competent court;

(b) the lawful arrest or detention of a person for non-compliance with the lawful order of a court or in order to secure the fulfilment of any obligation prescribed by law;

(c) the lawful arrest or detention of a person effected for the purpose of bringing him before the competent legal authority of reasonable suspicion of having committed and

³⁹ This interpretation derives from the drafting of the ICCPR. UN documents A/2929, chapter VI, s. 29,30 and 31; A/4045, s. 49; as cited in Nihal Jayawickrama, *The Judicial Application of Human Rights Law* (2006), p. 376.

⁴⁰ *A v. Australia*, Human Rights Committee, Communication No. 560/1993, HCR 1997 Report Annex V.I.L.

⁴¹ UN Working Group on Arbitrary Detention, as cited in Nihal Jayawickrama, *supra* footnote n. 40, p. 377.

⁴² While the ECHR includes the language requirement, the ICCPR does not explicitly include this requirement.

offence or when it is reasonably considered necessary to prevent his committing an offence or fleeing after having done so;
(d) the detention of a minor by lawful order for the purpose of educational supervision or his lawful detention for the purpose of bringing him before the competent legal authority;
(e) the lawful detention of persons for the prevention of the spreading of infectious diseases, of persons of unsound mind, alcoholics or drug addicts, or vagrants;
(f) the lawful arrest or detention of a person to prevent his effecting an unauthorized entry into the country or of a person against whom action is being taken with a view to deportation or extradition.”

Article 5(4) ECHR states:

“4. Everyone who is deprived of his liberty by arrest or detention shall be entitled to take proceedings by which the lawfulness of his detention shall be decided speedily by a court and his release ordered if the detention is not lawful.”

Article 5(1) protects liberty and security of person and provides an exhaustive list of six exceptions to the right to liberty. Article 5(1)(f) includes immigration detention as one of these exceptions, although this does not mean that all forms of immigration detention are permitted by Article 5.

ECHR Test: Was it “a procedure prescribed by law”?

Immigration detention must not only be in line with substantive and procedural rules of Italian national law. The Article 5(1) right to liberty and security of person would be violated if a migrant’s arrest was “unlawful” on the basis that it did not follow a “procedure prescribed by law”⁴³.

ECHR Test: Was the arrest in line with the purpose of Article 5(1)?

Even if a person’s arrest complies with Italian national law, it is still possible for an arrest allowed in the national law to breach Article 5(1) in the case that the arrest in question was not consistent with the purpose of Article 5, namely, to protect the individual from arbitrariness⁴⁴. This could be relevant in the case of *en masse* arrests that do not take individual circumstances into consideration. It could also be relevant if there is an abuse of power, such as a misleading arrest like luring a person to a police station under other pretences, so that the police could then detain that person⁴⁵.

Directive 2008/115/EC Test: Considering the purposes of and alternatives to detention

In addition to the ECHR Article 5 requirements, Article 15(1) of Directive 2008/115/EC further stipulates that Italy can only detain a person for immigration reasons when:

- There are no other sufficient but less coercive measures that can be applied effectively in a specific case; and
- The third country national in detention is subject to return procedures; and
- If detention is used by Italy in order to prepare the return and/or carry out the removal, it should be used in particular when:
 - There is a risk of absconding (Article 15(1)(a)); or

⁴³ *Bonzo v. France*, European Court of Human Rights, judgment of 18 December 1986, Series A no. 111; *Chahal v. The United Kingdom*, European Court of Human Rights, judgment of 15 November 1996.

⁴⁴ *Čonka v. Belgium*, European Court of Human Rights, judgement of 2 February 2002, para. 39.

⁴⁵ *Čonka v. Belgium*, European Court of Human Rights, judgment of 2 February 2002.

- The third country national concerned avoids or hampers the preparation of return or removal process (Article 15(1)(b)).

Such detention shall be:

- for as short a period as possible; and
- only maintained so long as the removal arrangements are in progress and executed with due diligence (Article 15(1)).

ECHR Test: Do the conditions of detention violate Article 5(1)?

Article 5(1) ECHR can be violated on account of the conditions of detention or remand. The European Court of Human Rights has ruled that there must be a relationship between the “ground of permitted deprivation of liberty relied on and the place and conditions of detention”⁴⁶. Furthermore, the systemic, routine or widespread use of detention for asylum seekers is contrary to the principle of *non refoulement*⁴⁷.

ECHR Test: Narrow interpretation rule

The exceptions for detention under Article 5 ECHR should be given a narrow interpretation⁴⁸.

ECHR Test: Was the detainee given their entitlement to question the lawfulness of their detention in a Court?

The above appears to be applicable also to immigration detention. Moreover, Directive 2008/115/EC specifies:

- Return decisions and entry ban decisions “*shall be issued in writing and give reasons in fact and in law as well as information about available legal remedies*”⁴⁹
 - This right to receive reasons in fact may be limited by Italian national law when such right to information is restricted in order to safeguard national security, defence, public security and/or for the prevention, detection and prosecution of criminal offences
- If a third country national has legally entered Italy, then upon request Italy “*shall provide a written or oral translation of the main elements of decisions related to return [...] including information on the available legal remedies in a language the third country national understands or may reasonably be presumed to understand*”⁵⁰. However, if the third country national did not enter Italy legally, then the above is not an obligation⁵¹.
- In the case of migrants who entered the country illegally and stayed illegally, Italy is obliged to issue a return decision in writing “*by means of a standard form as set out under national legislation*” and Italy must also “*make available generalised information sheets explaining the main elements of the standard form in at least five*

⁴⁶ *Mayeka and Kaniki Mitunga v Belgium*, European Court of Human Rights, judgment of 12 October 2006, para. 102; see also *mutatis mutandis*, *Aerts v. Belgium*, European Court of Human Rights, judgment of 30 July 1998, para. 46.

⁴⁷ Committee of Ministers of the Council of Europe, *Guidelines on human rights protection in the context of accelerated asylum procedures*, adopted by the Committee of Ministers of the Council of Europe on 1 July 2009 at the 1062nd meeting of the Ministers’ Deputies (European Guidelines on accelerated asylum procedures), Guideline 3.

⁴⁸ *Kurt v. Turkey*, European Court of Human Rights, judgment of 25 May 1998, para. 122.

⁴⁹ Directive 2008/115/EC, art. 12(1).

⁵⁰ Directive 2008/115/EC, art. 12(2).

⁵¹ Directive 2008/115/EC, art. 12(3).

of those languages which are most frequently used or understood by illegal migrants entering the Member State concerned”⁵².

The Right to Respect for Private and Family Life

The Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms (ECHR)

Article 8 of the ECHR states:

“1. Everyone has the right to respect for his private and family life, his home and his correspondence.

2. There shall be no interference by a public authority with the exercise of this right except such as is in accordance with the law and is necessary in a democratic society in the interests of national security, public safety or the economic well-being of the country, for the prevention of disorder or crime, for the protection of health or morals, or for the protection of the rights and freedoms of others.”

ECHR Article 8 Test:

Stage 1:

- 1.1 Does the complaint fall within the scope of one of the rights protected by Article 8(1)?
- 1.2 If so, is there a positive obligation on the State to respect an individual’s right and has it been fulfilled?

Stage 2:

- 2.1 Has there been an interference with the Article 8 right?
Once it is established that the dispute concerns an Article 8 right, the next stage of the test is to determine whether the measure complained of interferes with that right. Examples include:
 - removing children from their parents and taking them into public care;
 - stopping prisoners correspondence;
 - searching a person’s home; or
 - gathering and storing information on a secret police file.
- 2.2 If so;
 - 2.2.1 Is it in accordance with law?
 - 2.2.2 Does it pursue a legitimate aim?
 - 2.2.3 Is it necessary in a democratic society?

It is up to the applicant to characterise the interest which they seek to protect and to advance their argument before the European Court of Human Rights (“the Court”).

Whilst the Court has avoided strict and exclusive clarification of Article 8 ECHR, there are nevertheless some important and precise notions. For example, private life includes relationships between foster parents and children they have looked after, *de facto* couples and same-sex relationships regardless of whether they have children.

⁵² Id.

As a rule, the Court decides on the **existence of family life on the facts of each case**. The general question to ask is whether there are close personal ties between the parties. Although the Court's case-by-case approach means that it is not always possible to enumerate those relationships which constitute family life and those which do not, an increasing number of relationships now enjoy the automatic protection of Article 8.

The family based on marriage:

1. The protection of Article 8 always extends to marriages, which can be shown to be lawful and genuine. Those lacking substance or existing in form only, such as a sham marriage entered into for the purposes of avoiding immigration rules or acquiring nationality, may thus fall outside the scope of Article 8.
2. A child born to parents who are lawfully and genuinely married will be *ipso iure* part of that relationship from the moment and by the fact of the child's birth. Thus, the relationship between married parents and their children will always fall within the scope of Article 8(1).

Is marriage necessary to enjoy family life?

- Article 8 applies automatically to the relationship between a mother and her child, regardless of her marital status. Therefore, such relationships will always require the protection of Article 8.
- Unmarried couples who live together with their children will normally be said to enjoy family life.

Family life can also exist between:

- Children and their grandparents, since they play a significant part in family life;
- Siblings, both as children and as adults;
- The relationship between an uncle or aunt and his/her nephew or niece may fall within the meaning of family life where there is particular evidence of close personal ties;
- Family life may exist between parents and children born into second relationships, or those children born as a result of an extra-marital or adulterous affair, particularly where the paternity of the children has been recognised and the parties enjoy close personal ties;
- The relationship between adoptive parents who enjoy close personal ties; and
- Whether ties between a child and their foster parents will amount to family life will depend on the facts of the case, in particular, whether the child has close personal ties with their natural parents and the length of time that they were in the foster family's care. The longer the foster-care arrangement, the greater the likelihood that family ties will be found to exist.

The individual circumstances of the case are vital to determining questions relating to family life. The implementation of Article 8 ECHR is complex and must consider family conditions as well as children's rights law, which places the best interests of the child as a primary consideration in all judicial decisions.

The Prohibition on Torture, Inhumane or Degrading Treatment

The Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms (ECHR)

Article 3 of the ECHR states:

“No one shall be subjected to torture or to inhuman or degrading treatment or punishment.”

ECHR Article 3 Test: What is torture?

Requirements:

- The infliction of severe mental or physical pain or suffering;
- The intentional or deliberate infliction of the pain; and
- The pursuit of a specific purpose, such as gaining information, punishment or intimidation.

Torture has a purpose and it is deliberately exercised. The physical or mental consequences of torture are serious. In the context of immigration detention, we are more likely to consider whether conduct meets the definition of inhumane and degrading treatment (e.g. corporal punishment could be considered to be degrading treatment). Furthermore, the sex, age and conditions of the ill-treated or tortured person should be taken into careful consideration when determining whether Article 3 ECHR has been breached. Article 3 ECHR is also relevant to cases of war, persecution, and public emergency as well as reasonable risks that foreigners will be subject to torture or ill-treatment in their country of origin.

Burden of Proof:

Where a detainee shows signs of injuries, or ill-health, either upon release or at any stage during their detention, the burden will be on the detaining authorities to establish that the signs or symptoms are unrelated to the period or fact of detention.

Examples of the kinds of conduct that has constituted torture:

- Palestinian hanging: suspension by the arms, tied behind the back (*Aksoy v. Turkey*⁵³);
- Electric shocks (*Akkoç v. Turkey*⁵⁴);
- Rape (*Aydin v. Turkey*⁵⁵);
- Falaka/falanga: beatings on the soles of the feet (*Salman v. Turkey*⁵⁶);
- Severe beating (*Selmouni v. France*⁵⁷);
- Severe beatings, combined with denial of medical treatment (*Ilhan v. Turkey*⁵⁸); and
- The cumulative effect of cell conditions – in the past the European Court of Human Rights has considered factors such as a dirty and dilapidated premises, flooding, lack

⁵³ European Court of Human Rights, judgment of 18 December 1996.

⁵⁴ European Court of Human Rights, judgment of 10 October 2000.

⁵⁵ European Court of Human Rights, judgment of 25 September 1997.

⁵⁶ European Court of Human Rights, judgment of 27 June 2000.

⁵⁷ European Court of Human Rights, judgment 28 July 1999,

⁵⁸ European Court of Human Rights, GC no. 22277/93, ECHR 2000–VII.

of sufficient light for reading and writing, the detainee's health conditions, size of the cell⁵⁹.

In determining whether Article 3 ECHR has been violated it is necessary to consider all of the circumstances of detention. For example, in *Ananyev and Others v. Russia (nos. 42525/07 and 60800/08)*⁶⁰ the European Court of Human Rights held that authorities needed to improve the material conditions of detention by:

- shielding the toilets in cells, removing thick netting from cell windows and increasing the frequency of showers;
- changing the applicable legal framework, as well as practices and attitudes;
- ensuring that pre-trial detention is only used in absolutely necessary cases;
- establishing maximum capacity for each remand prison;
- and ensuring that victims can complain effectively about inadequate conditions of detention and that they would obtain appropriate compensation.

Three safeguards growing from Article 3 ECHR and connected to Article 5 ECHR:

1. The right of the detainee to have a third party of their choice notified of their detention (i.e. a family member, friend or consulate);
2. The right to access a lawyer; and
3. The right to request a medical examination by a doctor of their choice.

Violations of Article 3 must be determined on a case-by-case basis and factors to consider include overcrowding, lack of outdoor exercise for all prisoners, forced feeding and compulsory medical intervention, lack of medical attention, lack of contact with the outside world, inadequate standards of hygiene and toilet facilities (and hygiene in cells), strip searches of prisoners and lack of adequate medical or dental care. For example, in *Mandic and Jovic v. Slovenia*⁶¹, the violation of Article 3 was grounded on the fact that the available cell was 2.7m² and the temperature inside was 28°C. Furthermore, the Court argued that authorities are under an obligation to protect the health of people who have been deprived of their liberty.

Freedom of Thought, Conscience and Religion

The Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms (ECHR)

Article 9 of the ECHR states:

“1. Everyone has the right to freedom of thought, conscience and religion; this right includes freedom to change his religion or belief and freedom, either alone or in community with others and in public or private, to manifest his religion or belief, in worship, teaching, practice and observance.

⁵⁹ *Payet v France*, European Court of Human Rights, judgment of 20 January 2011; *Modârca v. Moldova*, European Court of Human Rights, judgment of 10 May 2007.

⁶⁰ European Court of Human Rights, judgment of 10 January 2012.

⁶¹ European Court of Human Rights, judgment of 20 October 2011.

2. *Freedom to manifest one's religion or beliefs shall be subject only to such limitations as are prescribed by law and are necessary in a democratic society in the interests of public safety, for the protection of public order, health or morals, or for the protection of the rights and freedoms of others.*"

The Right to a Fair Trial

The first hurdle to exercising the right to a fair trial in immigration matters involves distinguishing between those provisions that apply to immigration cases and those which only apply to criminal law cases. The main general provisions in relation to the right to a fair trial are outlined below.

The Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR)

Article 10 of the UDHR states:

"Everyone is entitled in full equality to a fair and public hearing by an independent and impartial tribunal, in the determination of his rights and obligations and of any criminal charge against him."

The International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR)

Article 14(1) of the ICCPR states:

"1. All persons shall be equal before the courts and tribunals. In the determination of any criminal charge against him, or of his rights and obligations in a suit at law, everyone shall be entitled to a fair and public hearing by a competent, independent and impartial tribunal established by law. The press and the public may be excluded from all or part of a trial for reasons of morals, public order (ordre public) or national security in a democratic society, or when the interest of the private lives of the parties so requires, or to the extent strictly necessary in the opinion of the court in special circumstances where publicity would prejudice the interests of justice; but any judgement rendered in a criminal case or in a suit at law shall be made public except where the interest of juvenile persons otherwise requires or the proceedings concern matrimonial disputes or the guardianship of children."

The Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms (ECHR)

Article 6(1) of the ECHR states:

"1. In the determination of his civil rights and obligations or of any criminal charge against him, everyone is entitled to a fair and public hearing within a reasonable time by an independent and impartial tribunal established by law. Judgement shall be pronounced publicly by the press and public may be excluded from all or part of the trial in the interest of morals, public order or national security in a democratic society, where the interests of juveniles or the protection of the private life of the parties so require, or the extent strictly necessary in the opinion of the court in special circumstances where publicity would prejudice the interests of justice."

In general, expulsion and extradition procedures are outside the scope of Article 6 ECHR, and Article 1 of Protocol No. 7 is limited to non-citizens who are lawfully resident in a contracting state. Consequently, Article 13 ECHR on the right to an effective remedy is often the most important ECHR provision in relation to procedural safeguards in immigration cases.

However, Article 6(1) ECHR might be relevant and is worth considering in case of:

- a failure to process an asylum (or other) claim and the refusal to re-commence the asylum process;
- conditions of detention affecting the fairness of legal proceedings;
- decisions to expel entire groups of people that are not made on an individual basis; or
- the unavailability of a fair and public hearing to challenge their detention within a reasonable time and by an independent and impartial tribunal.

The question of whether the European Court of Human Rights should adopt a liberal definition of “civil rights and obligations” under Article 6(1) has received mixed opinions from the bench. In their dissenting judgment in *Maaouia v. France*⁶², Judge Loucaises and Judge Traja argued that in order to interpret Article 6(1) ECHR in good faith, Article 6(1) must be broadly interpreted to mean those actions that are non-criminal, as per Article 31(a) of the Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties. Here, Judge Loucaises was influenced by what he interpreted to be the purpose of Article 6(1) as well as the fact scenario before him and how the good faith requirement would be reflected in the phrase “civil rights and obligations”:

“Article 1 of Protocol 7 was aimed at the establishment of a protection vis-à-vis the administration which in any case could not serve as a substitute for the judicial guarantees of Article 6 or even minimise the negative effects resulting from the absence of the latter. This protection in question may very well be supplementary to the judicial guarantees of Article 6.”⁶³

ECHR Test: Prohibition on *en masse* expulsion:

Article 4 of Protocol No. 4 prohibits *en masse* expulsion of foreigners, deeming it to be unlawful.

⁶² European Court of Human Rights, judgment of 5 October 2000, paras. 37-39.

⁶³ From the dissenting judgment of Judge Loucaises and Judge Traja in *Maaouia v. France* (paras. 37-38).

The Right to an Effective Remedy

The Convention on the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms (ECHR)

Article 13 of the ECHR states:

“Everyone whose rights and freedoms as set forth in this Convention are violated shall have an effective remedy before a national authority notwithstanding that the violation has been committed by persons acting in an official capacity.”

According to Hélène Lambert, “The rationale of Article 13 is to secure, at national level, a remedy to enforce the substance of the rights and freedoms guaranteed in the ECHR, in whatever form that remedy takes in the domestic legal order”⁶⁴.

ECHR Article 13 Test: on what constitutes an “effective remedy”

Broadly speaking, to be an “effective remedy” the remedy must:

1. Exist institutionally (in the national legal framework). The Court looks at the capacity of the local authority to provide effective remedy in practice and in law;
2. The “remedy must be organised in such a way as to allow the competent national authority to deal with the substance of the complaint and to grant appropriate relief”⁶⁵ (see *Chahal v. the United Kingdom*⁶⁶);
3. The remedy must be available to the individual.

The last point (3) is particularly relevant to Italian immigration detention because it means that examples of breaching the right to an effective remedy could include:

- A case where a person’s asylum application is rejected and the asylum applicant does not then have access to an appeal procedure. In this sense a lack of “access” could exist where the rejected applicant is not in a position to initiate such an appeal⁶⁷.
- If an applicant for asylum is rejected and they initiated an appeal against the rejection but the appeal process did not have a staying effect on deportation proceedings (i.e. removal was effectuated before the outcome of the appeal had been decided)⁶⁸.
- If a detainee is prevented from requesting judicial review or legal representation then their right to an effective remedy before a national authority has been breached. For example, in *Čonka v. Belgium*⁶⁹ the Court noted that the applicants also could have telephoned out to obtain legal advice, however the Court took into consideration that the applicants were convinced it was impossible to appeal their decision and therefore the Court held that in effect Article 13 ECHR had been breached.
- Situations where a detainee believes that challenging the detention would be impossible.
- Situations where the detainee does not have an effective national-level remedy for enforcing the substance of the ECHR rights and freedoms.

⁶⁴ Hélène Lambert, “The position of aliens in relation to the European Convention on Human Rights”, Council of Europe Publishing, 2006, p. 36.

⁶⁵ Id.

⁶⁶ European Court of Human Rights, judgment of 15 November 1996.

⁶⁷ See Commission’s report on *Plattform “Arzte fur das Leben” v. Austria*, judgment of 21 June 1988; *R v. Secretariat of State for Social Security, ex parte Re B and Joint Council for Welfare Immigrants (JCWI)*, [1997] 1 WLR 275.

⁶⁸ See *Soering v. the United Kingdom*, European Court of Human Rights, judgment of 7 July 1989.

⁶⁹ European Court of Human Rights, judgement of 2 February 2002.

Religious Rights: Freedom of Thought, Conscience and Religion

The Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms (ECHR)

Article 9 of the ECHR states:

“1. Everyone has the right to freedom of thought, conscience and religion; this right includes freedom to change his religion or belief and freedom, either alone or in community with others and in public or private, to manifest his religion or belief, in worship, teaching, practice and observance.

2. Freedom to manifest one’s religion or beliefs shall be subject only to such limitations as are prescribed by law and are necessary in a democratic society in the interests of public safety, for the protection of public order, health or morals, or for the protection of the rights and freedoms of others.”

Therefore, if there is an interference with religious rights, it must be justified on the grounds of being prescribed by law and necessary in a democratic society. Every detainee should have a right to worship and to meet a priest, imam or any other religious leader.

Further Research on the European and International Framework concerning Immigration Detention

Other International Treaties and Protocols

- *Convention Relating to the Status of Refugees* (1951) and the *Protocol Relating to the Status of Refugees* (1967)
- *Vienna Convention on Consular Relations* (1963)
- *International Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Racial Discrimination* (1965)
- *International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights* (1966)
- *Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women* (1979)
- *Convention against Torture and Other Cruel, Inhuman, or Degrading Treatment or Punishment* (1984) and the *Optional Protocol to the Convention against Torture and Other Cruel, Inhuman, or Degrading Treatment or Punishment* (2002)
- *Convention on the Rights of the Child* (1989) and the *Optional Protocol to the Convention on the Rights on the Sale of Children, Child Prostitution, and Child Pornography* (2000)
- *International Convention on the Protection of the Rights of All Migrant Workers and Members of Their Families* (1990)
- *Protocol to Prevent, Suppress, and Punish Trafficking in Persons, Especially Women and Children, supplementing the United Nations Convention against Transnational Organized Crime* (2000)
- *Protocol against the Smuggling of Migrants by Land, Sea, and Air , supplementing the United Nations Convention against Transnational Organized Crime* (2000)
- *The European Convention for the Prevention of Torture and Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment* (1987)
- *Council of Europe Convention on Action against Trafficking in Human Beings* (2005)

UN Declarations, Principles, Guidelines

- *Standard Minimum Rules for the Treatment of Prisoners* (1977)
- *Declaration on the Human Rights of Individuals Who Are not Nationals of the Country in which They Live* (1985)
- *Body of Principles for the Protection of All Person under Any Form of Detention or Imprisonment* (1988)
- *Rules for the Protection of Juveniles Deprived of their Liberty* (1990)

The European Parliament's Findings and Recommendations (2007)

In 2007 the European Parliament's Policy Department on Citizens' Rights and Constitutional Affairs published a report titled, "*The conditions in centres for third country national (detention camps, open centres as well as transit centres and transit zones) with a particular focus on provisions and facilities for persons with special needs in the 25 EU Member States*". Pages 13 and 108 of the report provide a plain English overview of the Italian detention system, as well as the problems and recommendations highlighted by the researchers. The research that was collected by the European Parliament came from the Italian organisation ARCI (Italian Cultural and Recreation Association).

Glossary

Avvocato di fiducia → An *avvocato di fiducia* is a lawyer whom a person has individually chosen to represent them for a case.

Avvocato di ufficio → An *avvocato d'ufficio* is a lawyer appointed by the judge or the prosecution in cases where legal assistance is required by law but a person did not nominate their own lawyer.

Camera di Consiglio → *Camera di consiglio* is a special proceeding through which the dispute is resolved in a faster and private way without audience and with limited *istruttoria*.

Carabinieri → The *Carabinieri* is one of the five Italian police branches. It is under the authority of the Ministry of Defence. Similarly to *Polizia di Stato*, the *Carabinieri*'s main functions are: maintaining order, ensuring public security and preventing crimes. The *Carabinieri* is also part of the Italian army, so it is a military police branch. Its full name is the *Arma dei Carabinieri*.

Commissione Territoriale → The *Commissione Territoriale per il Riconoscimento della Protezione Internazionale* is an administrative body under the authority of the Ministry of the Interior. Its function is to examine and decide on the applications for the recognition of the refugee status or the subsidiary protection status. There are ten *Commissioni Territoriali* in Italy. Each of them is competent over a territory that comprises a number of provinces.

Contraddittorio → In the context of immigration detention, *contraddittorio* essentially guarantees the right of the foreigner to a full defence in the course of the validation and extension hearings, granting his participation and his right to be heard by the *Giudice di Pace*.

Corte di Cassazione → The *Corte di Cassazione* is the Italian Supreme Court located in Rome. It is a *giudice di legittimità*, which means that it cannot undertake merits review and it can only hear judicial review questions about the interpretation of law and procedural correctness. Moreover, it solves conflicts about jurisdiction.

Giudice di Pace → A *Giudice di Pace* is a non-specialist small-claims judge who is in charge of resolving minor cases or disputes under civil, administrative or criminal law, lacking the power to inflict custodial sentences. In Italian, a *Giudice di Pace* is commonly called an “honorary judge” (*giudice onorario*) who is appointed by the Minister of Justice. *Giudici di Pace* are paid depending on the number of cases they decide on. Generally the selected *Giudici di Pace* are law graduates who have obtained the qualification to practice law or who have exercised judicial functions. Unlike in some jurisdictions, in Italy it is not necessary to have years of experience as a lawyer or barrister before undertaking the *Giudice di Pace* role. The only further requirement is that a *Giudice di Pace* must be between thirty and sixty-five years of age.

Giudice togato → A *giudice togato* is a judge who exercises a judicial function and they are appointed via an open and competitive application process.

Gratuito patrocinio → *Gratuito patrocinio* is free legal assistance provided by law when a person cannot afford the cost of a lawyer. In many English jurisdictions, this is called “legal aid”.

Guardia di Finanza → The *Guardia di Finanza* is a military branch of the Italian police. It is under the authority of the Ministry of Economics and Finance. Although the *Guardia di Finanza* is part of the Italian army, it features special competences in the prevention and repression of financial and fiscal crimes. It is a military police branch.

Istruttoria → *Istruttoria* is the initial stage of a legal procedure in which the Court collects all of the necessary elements for the next step of the proceeding. In the *istruttoria* phase the judge carries out investigations and acquires evidence and relevant information for the final judgement.

Prefetto → The *Prefetto* is the head of the Italian *Prefettura*.

Prefettura → The *Prefettura* is the local branch of the Ministry of the Interior and it represents the central government at a local level. In each of the 110 Italian provinces (*Province*) there is a *Prefettura*. *Prefettura* offices manage issues such as order and public security, civil rights and immigration, local autonomies and voting matters.

Questore → The *Questore* is the head of the Italian *Questura*.

Questura → The *Questura* is an office of the *Polizia di Stato* that is under the authority of the Ministry of the Interior and is competent in the territory of the province (*Provincia*) where it is located. *Questura*'s main function consists in maintaining order and ensuring public security within the territory of the province.

Useful Websites and Articles on Migration and Immigration Detention in Europe

http://www.asgi.it/home_asgi.php?

The homepage for the ASGI (*Associazione per gli Studi Giuridici sull'Immigrazione*).

<http://www.autistici.org/macerie/>

A blog containing information about Turin's and Milan's CIEs, in Italian.

<http://www.borderline-europe.de/>

Borderline Europe's website.

<http://www.cestim.it/>

An Italian website that shares publications, research and thesis on migration in Italy, in Italian.

<http://www.corriereimmigrazione.it/>

An Italian online journal on migration issues, in Italian.

www.detention-in-europe.org

See also:

- http://detention-in-europe.org/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=220&Itemid=242

This link contains information about the DEVAS Project, which was conducted by the Jesuit Refugees Service Europe and investigated conditions of detention for asylum seekers in all twenty-seven EU Member States.

- http://detention-in-europe.org/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=147&Itemid=179

This link provides an overview of the Italian detention system with links to various reports written on the Italian system (the reports date back to 2006 and 2007).

[http://fortresseurope.blogspot.com/search/label/CIE?updated-max=2011-07-20%2018T17%3A05%3A00%2B02%3A00&max-results=20.](http://fortresseurope.blogspot.com/search/label/CIE?updated-max=2011-07-20%2018T17%3A05%3A00%2B02%3A00&max-results=20)

A blog by Gabriele del Grande, a well-known Italian journalist and migration expert and it includes relevant information and specific updates on Turin's CIE.

<http://www.globaldetentionproject.org/countries/europe/italy/introduction.html>

<http://www.google.it/url?sa=t&rct=j&q=practical+responses+to+irregular+migration&source=web&cd=3&ved=0CDgQFjAC&url=http%3A%2F%2Femn.intrasoft-intl.com%2FDownloads%2Fdownload.do%3Bjsessionid%3D025582BD421431F0E9118882431DCEC0%3FfileID%3D2472&ei=tIU5T7zXCsjN4QTBn4mhCw&usq=AFQjCNEykvj0CFqEay3oSX3pL58UdJtZA>

Practical Responses to Irregular Migration: The Italian Case, edited by EMN (European Migration Network), Rome, 2012.

<http://idcoalition.org/>

<http://www.immigrazione.it/>

An online journal for professionals that publishes law and cases on immigration in Italy (in Italian).

<http://www.interno.it/mininterno/export/sites/default/it/assets/files/1/2007131181826.pdf>

Commissione De Mistura Investigation on national CIE system (2007) (in Italian).

<http://www.lasciatecentrare.it/>

An active national network of NGOs campaigning for the suppression of CIE (in Italian).

<http://www.meltingpot.org/>

An Italian online journal on migration issues (in Italian).

http://www.jrseurope.org/news_releases/OctLampedusaLifestory.pdf

An article for *L'Espresso* about detention in CIE by Fabrizio Gatti.

<https://migrantsatsea.wordpress.com/>

A blog about migrants crossing the Mediterranean Sea.

<http://www.migreurop.org/>

A transnational network lobbying against confinement and detention of migrants (in Italian, French, English, Spanish and German).

<http://www.openaccessnow.eu/it/>

A European association advocating for the right to access immigration detention centres (in Italian, French and English).

<http://picum.org/en>

A platform for international cooperation on issues that face undocumented migrants.

<http://www.redattoresociale.it/>

An Italian online journal that includes information on migration issues (in Italian).

<http://www.ristretti.org/>

A website that publishes news about prison and immigration detention centres. See the section called “research” for research on immigration (in Italian).

<http://www.statewatch.org/analyses/no-165-eu-north-africa.pdf>

An article published in Statewatch by Yasha Maccanico titled “The EU’s self-interested response to unrest in north Africa: the meaning of treaties and readmission agreements between Italy and north African states”.

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